

INDEX NUMBER.....

H FNMTC - BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - MAY 2019
RM14: ADVANCED MIDWIFERY AND THEATRE NURSING: RMD 323
TIME ALLOWED: 1:30MINS

OBJECTIVES

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

- a. The maintenance of asepsis sometimes means going to what may be considered unnecessary measures by those who do not understand the many possibilities of introducing infection.
Outline FIVE (5) basic principles in aseptic techniques in theatre. - 5 marks
- b. We know that bacteria are over present and a seemingly minor error in technique may cause a wound to become infected. We must resolve to prevent infection by the faithful practice of aseptic technique. Briefly mention FIVE (5) common sources of wound infection in theatre.
- 5 marks
- c. A 55 year old Banker is admitted to the ward for hysterectomy the next day. You have been assigned to prepare the patient for the operation. In not less than five(5) points how would you prepare the patient under the following headings
- i. Physiological preparation - 5 marks
- ii. Psychological preparation - 5 marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. Safiatu Adamu, a pregnant woman at term has been admitted to the ward with complains of lower abdominal pains since two hours ago. On examination, she was fully dilated with adequate contractions but poor maternal effort. Estimated foetal weight (4.5kgs,) CTG shows heart rate of 180bpm. Baby delivered through episiotomy. Heart rate less than 100bpm but baby not breathing or crying.
- i. Outline the processes in Neonatal Resuscitation - 6 marks
- ii. Give eight instruments/ materials you will need to suture the episiotomy - 4 marks
- iii. Name four general anaesthesia drugs you know - 2 marks
- iv. List four regional anaesthesia drugs you know - 2 marks
- b. The woman above is scheduled to receive 3 litres of normal saline in 24 hours
Calculate the total drops per minutes given that the drop factor is 15
- Formula - 2marks
- Calculation - 2marks
- Answer - 2 marks

QUESTION THREE

Identify the following obstetrics/Gynaecological instruments and state **two** functions ,
two procedures that the instruments can be used for

A

B

C

D

Name: 1 mark, Function: 2 marks, procedures use in: 2 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....

HFNMTC – BEREKUM

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- AUGUST, 2021

RM 16 CODE: RMD 323 ADVANCED MIDWIFERY AND THEATRE NURSING

TIME: 1HR.

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- *Answer all questions*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet*
- *Each question carries 20 marks.*
- *Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark*

QUESTION ONE

Madam Comfort Addo a 60years old woman is admitted to the hospital with a diagnosis of uterine myoma. She is scheduled for myomectomy. As an operating room nurse describe how you would;

- Receive madam comfort to the theatre - 10 marks
- Set up the operating room for surgery - 5marks
- Enumerate **FIVE** responsibilities as the circulating nurse - 5marks

QUESTION TWO

Madam Korkor had a spontaneous delivery. She retained some placenta products in the uterus and also had a cervical tear. She was rushed to the theatre for further management.

- State the type of surgery that would be performed for this client - 2marks
- State the positioning for this kind of surgery - 1mark
- Outline **FIVE (5)** other surgical positions and state the kind of surgery that positioning is employed - 5marks
- Mention **TWO (2)** risk factors associated with madam Korkors positioning and how to prevent this risk during surgery - 2marks
- State **FIVE (5)** instruments that can be used for this surgery and their uses - 10marks

INDEX NUMBER:.....
HFNMTC-BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-MAY 2018
RM 13 RDM 323ADVANCED MIDWIFERY / THEATRE NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HR

Instructions:

- *Answer all questions.*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate booklet*
- *Each question carries 20marks*
- *Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.*

Question One

Obstetric / gynaecological instruments

Identify the following instruments by their names, provide one function of each and give three procedures that the instruments can be used.

a.

b.

NMTC-BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-MAY 2016
RM 11 ADVANCED MIDWIFERY AND THEATRE NURSING

Question One

- a. Outline Ten (10) responsibilities each, of the following; Surgical Team members under the heading, Pre-Op. Intra –Op and Post – Operative stages
- i. Circulating nurse - 5 marks
 - ii. Scrub Nurse - 5 marks
- b. A 22 year old woman has been admitted and scheduled for laporotomy on an accounts of Ectopic Gestation. Blood pressure monitoring indicated as 90/60mmHg. After continuous recuscitaiton, she is to be given maintenance intravenous fluids of 2.5 litres in 24 hours
- i. Calculate the total drops per minutes, given that the drop factor is 15 drops per minutes - 4 marks
- c. Give the meaning of the following
- i. blepharo -
 - ii. lysis -
 - iii. Desis -
 - iv. Oscopy - 4 marks
- d. Define the word “Surgical hand Scrub” - 2 marks

Question Two

- a. List down five gynaecological instruments that are used during the following procedures.
- i. Pap smear
 - ii. Dilatation and curettage
 - iii. Evacuation of the uterus
- 15 marks
- b. Mention three (3) necessary reasons why cesarean sections are performed - 3 marks
- c. Give two (2) functions of Sims' speculum - 2 marks

Question Three

- a. It is very imperative to discuss with the patient undergoing surgical operation about the availability of pain management drugs at your facility. Mention two (2) side effects of non – steroidal Anti – inflammatory drugs (NSAID) under the following heading
- Gastrointestinal Tract
 - ii. Obstetrics
 - iii. Cardiovascular system
- b. Give four (4) indications of the following types of anaesthesia - 6 marks
- i. General Anaesthesia - 4 marks
 - ii. Regional Anaesthesia - 4 marks
- c. Give three examples of drugs of each of the following
- i. General Anaesthesia - 3 marks
 - ii. Regional Anaesthesia - 3 marks

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION JUNE 2014
RM – 9 & D 14 –HMDW 064 THEATRE NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ Hrs
Short Essay

INSTRUCTIONS:
Answer all questions.

1. What is the purpose of sterilization? - 4 marks
2. Briefly explain gowning. - 4 marks
3. The purpose of counting the sponges to be use in laporatomy is to ensure that. - 2 marks
4. At what stage does the circulating nurse count the used sponges. - 2 marks
5. A 45 years old Mr. Osam has been rushed to the theatre for Lumber puncture, suggest the preferred lumber region for lumber puncture to the newly posted medical officer who is to perform the procedure..... - 2marks
6. You have been asked to receive a new born at the operating theatre, which side of the patient on the bed would you position yourself to receive the baby. - 2 marks
7. For the first to five minutes post delivery of the new born by the surgeon, what action would you undertake? - 2 marks
8. How many kinds of sutures do we have? Mention them with 2 examples each. - 4 marks
9. Name the parts of the surgical needle - 4 marks
10. Name four (4) cardinal signs of wound infection - 4 marks
11. List the surgical team members - 4 marks
12. Rearrange the following the right order
Peritoniumskin.....fascia.....subcutaneous.....muscle - 4 marks
13. Madam Asaane, 38 weeks pregnant has been scheduled for caesarean section, her blood pressure is 80/40mmHg, as a theatre staff, you have been ordered to preload the patient.
Give two (2) examples of each of the following
i. Colloid - 2 marks
ii. Crystalloid - 2 marks
14. Outline the components of the following
i. Ringers lactate - 1 mark
ii. dextrose normal saline (DNS) - 1 mark
iii. 5% dextrose - 1 mark
iv. dick's plasma - 1 mark
15. How would you position Madam Otwey on the operating table who was 4 weeks pregnant and started spontaneous bleeding. She has been booked for Evacuation of the uterus (E. O. U).- 4 marks
16. Mention four (4) instruments that you known for evacuation of uterus - 4 marks

17. Rearrange and match the following against its meaning
- i. oscopy - 1 mark
 - ii. hysteron - 1 mark
 - iii. entero - 1 mark
 - iv. otomy - 1 mark
- A. Cutting into an organ or tissue
B. Intestine
C. Examination of an organ by viewing
D. Uterus
18. Mr. Sarfo complain of constipation for five (5) days now. X – ray shown perforation of small the intestine. He is to be given three (3) litres of intravenous fluid in 24 hours. Calculate the total drops per minutes, given that the drop factor is 15 drops/ minutes- 4 marks
19. Briefly outline the responsibilities of scrub nurse - 8 marks
20. Describe briefly scrubbing - 4 marks
21. Give the formulale for preparation of chlorine solution - 2 marks
22. Mention two (2) side effects of NSAID abuse of the following
- i. Pregnant mother - 2 marks
 - ii. Newborn - 2 marks
23. Give the meaning of the underlisted names
- i. Laporatomy - 1 mark
 - ii. Appendicectomy - 1 mark
 - iii. Herniorrhaphy - 1 mark
 - iv. C/S - 1 mark
24. Whys is it important to shave patient the day prior to surgery - 2 marks
25. Give full meaning of the following
- i. P. O. P - 1 mark
 - ii. D and C - 1 mark
 - iii. ORIF - 1 mark
 - iv. EX FIX - 1 mark

NMTC - BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION JUNE 2014
RM - 9 & D 14 - HMDW 064 THEATRE NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 1 1/2 Hrs
Short Essay

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